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Digital Era's Influence on Creative Nonfiction Pedagogy

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Abstract

The integration of personal experiences into writing, particularly in the digital era, presents new opportunities and challenges for students and educators. This study examines the impact of the digital era on the use of diary writing as a tool for fostering self-determined, creative, and didactic nonfiction learning. The focus is on integrating online-based diary writing into Creative Nonfiction pedagogy, aiming to transform teaching and learning into a more expressive, meaningful, and engaging experience in the context of new normal education. The research was conducted with Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences students at Culiati High School, employing a qualitative exploratory case study design. Data were gathered through a focus group discussion involving ten volunteer participants. Findings reveal that online-based diary writing enhances students' ability to express themselves, supports the development of writing proficiency, and contributes to both personal and professional growth. The study concludes that integrating digital tools into Creative Nonfiction pedagogy positively impacts teaching and learning, providing valuable insights for adapting education to the demands of the digital era.

Keywords: *digital era, diary writing, Creative Nonfiction, pedagogy, new normal education*

Introduction

The integration of personal experiences into writing, particularly in the digital era, presents new opportunities and challenges for students and educators. With widespread familiarity with digital tools, Creative Nonfiction has become increasingly accessible, especially for Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) students. Creative Nonfiction is often likened to jazz, as it encompasses a dynamic blend of ideas, styles, and techniques, drawing growing attention for its ability to nurture creativity and self-expression in a technology-driven world. Educators, parents, and researchers face the critical question of how to effectively prepare learners for future demands, particularly in writing factual and meaningful stories.

The internet, a cornerstone of modern life, has significantly influenced education by facilitating access to information and enabling efficient academic practices, including writing tasks (Harris, 2016). Abdalla (2020) emphasized that writing, an essential skill for communication and personal expression, is integral to students' academic journey, from simple content creation to complex compositions such as essays, poems, and short stories. Writing fosters cognitive and analytical skills, yet many students struggle to develop proficiency due to challenges such as limited vocabulary, weak argumentation, and insufficient practice (Anderson, 2017).

One approach to addressing these challenges is the use of online diary writing. Best Online Journal (2021) advocates for the convenience, accessibility, and privacy offered by digital diary platforms, which encourage regular writing practice. Qarina et al. (2018) highlighted the benefits of diary writing, including reflection, freedom of expression, and the development of writing fluency. These platforms provide students with a space to express their thoughts, recount personal experiences, and improve their writing skills through consistent practice.

Despite these advantages, students often encounter obstacles in writing, such as a lack of confidence, limited vocabulary, and difficulty visualizing ideas. These challenges are particularly pronounced in senior high school, where writing tasks are perceived as daunting. Teachers also face difficulties in designing effective techniques to teach writing, especially Creative Nonfiction. As part of the K-12 curriculum implemented in 2016, Creative Nonfiction is offered to Grade 12 HUMSS students in the Philippines. The subject introduces students to formal elements and techniques such as autobiography and blogging, aiming to develop critical and creative thinking skills to enhance their reading and writing capabilities.

However, teaching Creative Nonfiction in the Philippine context poses unique challenges due to language barriers and limited exposure to creative writing at the secondary level (Hidalgo, 2015). Teachers must adapt teaching strategies to address these issues while navigating the evolving demands of education during the pandemic (Jimenez, 2022). This study explores the potential of online diary writing as a pedagogical tool to address these challenges, transforming Creative Nonfiction instruction into a more accessible, meaningful, and engaging experience for students in the digital era.

Research Questions

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the description of students' learning experiences on the use of Filipino and English diary writing in Creative Non-Fiction?
2. What are the benefits of using online diary writing on the Creative Non-Fiction subject as perceived by the participants?
3. How does the use of online-based Filipino and English diary writing impact students' heutagogy in the Creative Non-Fiction?

subject?

Methodology

This study utilized homogeneous purposive sampling to select participants, focusing exclusively on Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) students enrolled in the Creative Nonfiction subject at Culiati High School during the first semester of the 2021–2022 school year. Five sections taught by the researcher incorporated online-based diary writing into their curriculum. Two volunteer students from each section, totaling ten participants, were selected for the study based on the quality of their written work and their willingness to contribute to the focus group discussions actively. Homogeneous purposive sampling ensures the inclusion of participants who share similar characteristics, facilitating a more detailed examination of the research focus (Dissertation.laerd.com, 2012).

The research employed a qualitative exploratory case study design to investigate the impact of online-based diary writing on students' self-determined learning in Creative Nonfiction. Data were primarily collected through focus group discussions guided by a validated interview protocol comprising one opening question, four probing questions, and one concluding question. The focus group discussions were conducted via Zoom, lasting approximately one hour, and facilitated by a professional moderator to minimize bias and enhance data reliability. The researcher transcribed the discussions, which were then verified by the participants to ensure accuracy and validity.

The data were analyzed using a deductive thematic analysis approach to align the findings with the Self-Determined Learning Theory. The analysis involved a five-step coding process: familiarization with the transcripts, generating initial codes, collating codes into themes, reviewing themes, and finalizing them. To enhance the integrity of the findings, three independent validators reviewed the developed themes. Thematic analysis enables the identification of patterns and relationships within the data, providing a structured method for interpreting qualitative information (Voxco.com, 2022).

An additional source of data was the students' online diaries, maintained on Google Docs using a standardized template provided by the researcher. Students documented their thoughts daily in either Filipino or English from September 2021 to January 2022, with optional entries on weekends. Diaries were submitted weekly, and the researcher provided monthly feedback to support students' reflective and creative writing development. The use of online diaries allowed participants to engage regularly with the writing process, fostering a deeper connection to their learning experience.

Ethical considerations were central to this study. Permissions were obtained from the school principal and division superintendent, and informed consent forms were secured from all participants. The focus group discussions were conducted with the assistance of an impartial moderator to uphold the integrity and minimize social interaction biases. The interview guide underwent validation by three experts to ensure clarity and appropriateness. Participants reviewed and confirmed the transcription of their contributions, further ensuring the accuracy and ethical handling of the data.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the salient findings of the gathered data to address the main objective: to investigate the impact of online-based Filipino and English diary writing on Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences students in their Creative Non-Fiction subject.

Students' Learning Experiences in Online Filipino and English Diary Writing in Creative Nonfiction

Online diary writing in Filipino and English has facilitated the development of essential skills among Grade 12 students in the Creative Nonfiction subject. Participants reported improvements in language proficiency, which involves accurate and appropriate language use in oral and written forms across diverse settings. This skill not only deepens one's understanding of language and culture but also enhances creativity, cognitive abilities, and analytical thinking. Several participants (e.g., 1, 2, 6, 7, 8, and 10) noted that this activity improved their vocabulary and their ability to select appropriate words for their writing. Additionally, online diary writing promoted self-expression, enabling students to convey their thoughts and emotions effectively. This outlet allowed participants to articulate their internal realities healthily and calmly, fostering personal growth. Furthermore, the practice encouraged self-reflection, helping students analyze experiences and derive meaningful insights, ultimately enhancing their critical thinking and evaluative skills.

Students Shared Perceptions of the Benefits of Online Creative Nonfiction Writing

The participants perceived several benefits from engaging in online diary writing. It supported their career development by honing skills relevant to their aspirations, such as effective communication and self-directed learning. It also contributed to emotional development, with some participants (e.g., 1, 2, and 6) highlighting how the activity provided a platform for managing emotions and expressing themselves. Additionally, the activity played a role in personality development, as it nurtured talents, enhanced skills, and facilitated personal transformation. These benefits collectively prepared the students for challenges beyond the academic context and fostered holistic growth.

The Impact of Online Diary Writing on Students' Heutagogy

The study analyzed the impact of online diary writing on students' heutagogy using three predefined categories of self-determination learning theory: autonomy, competence, and connection/relatedness. Autonomy was evident as students took ownership of their

learning journey, achieving goals through self-improvement, goal setting, self-evaluation, and self-remembrance. Competence was reflected in improved vocabulary, self-critique, and communication skills, with students demonstrating confidence in their ability to achieve desired outcomes. Connection/relatedness emerged as students shared personal thoughts, engaged with peers, and built trust, fostering a sense of belonging and interpersonal understanding.

Autonomy and Self-Determination in Learning

Autonomy, a cornerstone of heutagogy, was fostered as students developed a sense of psychological freedom and took the initiative in their learning processes. The diary writing activity encouraged self-improvement by enabling students to focus on personal growth and resilience. Participants also engaged in goal setting, which involved identifying objectives and creating actionable plans to achieve them. Through self-evaluation, students critically assessed their progress, identified areas for improvement, and became more independent in their learning. Moreover, self-remembrance allowed participants to reflect on their identity and experiences, fostering a deeper connection to their personal growth.

Competence and Connection in Learning

The development of competence was a significant outcome, as students reported enhanced vocabulary and communication skills, essential for effective interaction and expression. These skills also supported academic and career pursuits, enabling students to articulate ideas clearly and confidently. Connection/relatedness, another critical aspect of self-determination learning theory, was evident as students expressed their true selves, shared personal thoughts, and engaged with others. By building meaningful relationships, students experienced a sense of community and support, which enriched their learning experience and personal development. This sense of engagement underscored the human need for interconnectedness, as reflected in one participant's observation that the activity fostered active participation and interaction.

Conclusions

The primary aim of this study was to promote self-determined learning through the use of online diary writing in Creative Nonfiction. It sought to transform the teaching and learning of this genre into a more expressive, meaningful, and positive experience, particularly within the context of the "new normal" in education. The researcher observed that this approach fostered a deeper connection between students and the writing process, encouraging them to reflect, express, and engage with their work in ways that were both innovative and personal.

Through this study, the researcher recognized the significance of online diary writing as a powerful tool for fostering self-directed learning. Students embraced this pedagogical approach with enthusiasm, often expressing gratitude for the opportunities it provided. Their responses underscored how diary writing not only enhanced their writing skills but also cultivated their determination to learn independently. The daily practice, while initially demanding, resulted in noticeable progress as students consistently expanded their vocabulary, learning at least one new word each day.

The findings of this research emphasize the potential of diary writing pedagogy in enhancing students' learning experiences in the digital age. By integrating this method into their teaching, educators can inspire self-determined learning, creativity, and resilience in their students. The study also revealed that online diary writing simplifies the task of motivating students to develop writing skills, even amidst the challenges posed by the new normal in education.

As the researcher reflects on this journey, there is a renewed commitment to advocating for the integration of diary-writing pedagogy in both public and private educational settings. This practice has proven to be an effective means of fostering student engagement and self-directed learning in Creative Nonfiction, serving as a model for other subjects. By encouraging educators to explore this approach, the study aims to contribute to a broader transformation in teaching and learning, aligning with the demands and opportunities of the digital era.

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